

CURRENT VALUE OF CLINICAL AND PATHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE HEART IN HYPERTENSION DISEASE

Choriyeva Zulfia Yusupovna

Department of Anatomy and Clinical Anatomy, Tashkent Medical
Academy, Termiz branch: Senior teacher of anatomy:
choriyevazulfiya014@gmail.com

Aminova Mohinur Normurod kizi

Tashkent Medical Academy Termiz Branch No. 1 Faculty of Medicine
2nd stage student:

aminovamohinur133@gmail.com

Nomozova Kamola Nuriddin kizi

Tashkent Medical Academy Termiz branch No. 1 Faculty of Medicine
2nd stage student:

nomozovakamola817@gmail.com

Shukurova Barchinoy Abdulhafiz kizi

Tashkent Medical Academy Termiz Branch No. 2 Faculty of Medicine
2nd stage student: barchinoyshukurova018@gmail.com

Davlatova Dilnozakhon Olim kizi

Tashkent Medical Academy Termiz Branch No. 1 Faculty of Medicine
2nd stage student:

cvetocek021@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7575478>

Annotation: The heart plays the main role In hypertension (high blood pressure), the heart plays the main role. In these days, this disease is on the rise, and it affects not only the elderly, but also young children. This article of ours teaches how to prevent hypertension, explain it to people, and carry out treatment measures.

Keywords: Heart, Hypertension, Clinical signs, Pathological signs, Preventive measures, Symptoms.

Hypertension is a disease caused by a violation of the nervous-functional activity of blood vessels. It occurs mainly in people over 40 years of age, but in recent years, it has been observed more often in young people. Both men and women suffer from hypertension. If the disease is diagnosed in 20-30% of adults, after the age of 65, this indicator can be 50-65%. High blood pressure is one of the leading causes of death among patients with diseases of the cardiovascular system.

According to many experts, hypertension often occurs as a result of blood circulation disorders. Heart failure is also included in the list of its causes. This disease can trigger the development of secondary diseases in patients, including stroke and heart attack.

Scientists have been studying this disease for several decades. According to research, hypertension is one of the main causes of disability in our planet. According to statistics, if first aid is provided late when blood pressure increases, the condition of patients may worsen, and even death may occur.

The main symptom of hypertension is headache due to spasm and narrowing of cerebral vessels. Also, noise in the ears, decreased visual acuity, weakness, sleep disturbance, dizziness, heaviness in the head, increased heart rate are often manifested. These symptoms are noticeable in the early stages of the disease. Later, heart failure occurs due to long-term straining of the heart.

Heart failure is also one of the reasons for this. This disease can trigger the development of secondary diseases in patients, for example, we can cite diseases such as stroke and heart attack. High arterial blood pressure has a negative effect on blood vessels, because they can suddenly narrow for a short time. At very strong pressure, some blood vessels can burst and internal bleeding is observed. Hemorrhagic infarction occurs in areas where the vessels have lost their elasticity and are prone to fragility. It is a disease caused by the disruption of the nervous functional activity of blood vessels in a patient with hypertension. These diseases are more likely to occur in people over 40 years of age, but this disease is also observed in young people in these years. Hypertension affects women and men equally. This disease is a cardiovascular disease.

According to research, hypertonia is one of the main causes of disability in our planet. According to statistics, if first aid is provided late when blood pressure increases, the condition of patients may worsen and even death may occur. The main symptoms of high blood pressure are headaches due to spasm and narrowing of cerebral vessels. Noise in the ears, decreased visual acuity, weakness, sleep disturbance, dizziness, headache, and increased heart rate are also often manifested. These symptoms are felt in the human body in the middle stage of the disease. Later, due to the long-term strain of the heart, heart failure occurs, and the following diseases are easy nosebleeds, vomiting, insomnia, memory impairment, redness of the skin surface after some physical activity, strong pressure in the eyes, pain appears in the eyes that the patient looks around, so they like to lie down in a quiet and peaceful place with their eyes closed, rapid heartbeat, work in the tissues fever, fatigue occurs. In the current case, the causes of hypertension are related to the external environment, and the reason for the development of the disease is long-term stress and depression, frequent psychological stress. Often these are caused by work that requires constant emotional tension. In addition, concussion patients have a high risk of developing the disease. Hereditary predisposition is also among the reasons: if a person's generation has this disease, then the risk of developing this disease increases several times. The main factor influencing the development of the disease is a sedentary lifestyle. As people age, atherosclerosis may develop, and the increase in blood pressure against the background of this change makes the situation even more serious. This is considered very dangerous for life, because narrowed blood vessels can be harmful. If there are clots and cholesterol in the walls of the blood vessels, they separate during strong pressure and get stuck in the capillary blood vessels. In this case, a myocardial infarction or stroke occurs. The cause of high blood pressure in women may be hormonal during menopause. Salt, or more precisely, the sodium contained in it, as well as smoking, alcohol abuse, and obesity put pressure on the cardiovascular system.

Conclusion

Malnutrition is also a factor that causes hypertension. If a person consumes fatty meat, fried foods, smoked products and pickles more than the norm, it causes such a disease. It would be appropriate for everyone to include in their daily diet more products that help fight disease. For example, we can take vegetables, fruits, berries, greens, lean meat, beans, rice, buckwheat as an example. It is recommended that patients avoid any stress or emotional strain during treatment. Patients are recommended to walk in the open air: around the pond, in the garden, in the forest.

References:

- 1."High Blood Pressure Fact Sheet". CDC. 19 February 2015. Archived from the original on 6 March 2016. Retrieved 6 March 2016.
- 2.Jump up to:a b Lackland DT, Weber MA (May 2015). "Global burden of cardiovascular disease and stroke: hypertension at the core". *The Canadian Journal of Cardiology*. 31 (5): 569–571. doi:10.1016/j.cjca.2015.01.009. PMID 25795106.
- 3.Jump up to:a b Mendis S, Puska P, Norrving B (2011). *Global atlas on cardiovascular disease prevention and control (PDF) (1st ed.)*. Geneva: World Health Organization in collaboration with the World Heart Federation and the World Stroke Organization. p. 38. ISBN 9789241564373. Archived (PDF) from the original on 17 August 2014.
- 4.Jump up to:a b Hernandorena I, Duron E, Vidal JS, Hanon O (July 2017). "Treatment options and considerations for hypertensive patients to prevent dementia". *Expert Opinion on Pharmacotherapy (Review)*. 18 (10): 989–1000. doi:10.1080/14656566.2017.1333599. PMID 28532183. S2CID 46601689.
- 5.Safar ME, London GM (August 1987). "Arterial and venous compliance in sustained essential hypertension". *Hypertension*. 10 (2): 133–139. doi:10.1161/01.HYP.10.2.133. PMID 3301662.
- 6.Steppan J, Barodka V, Berkowitz DE, Nyhan D (2 August 2011). "Vascular stiffness and increased pulse pressure in the aging cardiovascular system". *Cardiology Research and Practice*. 2011: 263585. doi:10.4061/2011/263585. PMC 3154449. PMID 21845218.
- 7.Chobanian AV (August 2007). "Clinical practice. Isolated systolic hypertension in the elderly". *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 357 (8): 789–796. doi:10.1056/NEJMc071137. PMID 17715411. S2CID 42515260.
- 8.Zieman SJ, Melenovsky V, Kass DA (May 2005). "Mechanisms, pathophysiology, and therapy of arterial stiffness". *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*. 25 (5): 932–943. doi:10.1161/01.ATV.0000160548.78317.29. PMID 15731494.
- 9.Navar LG (December 2010). "Counterpoint: Activation of the intrarenal renin-angiotensin system is the dominant contributor to systemic hypertension". *Journal of Applied Physiology*. 109 (6): 1998–2000, discussion 2015. doi:10.1152/jappphysiol.00182.2010a. PMC 3006411. PMID 21148349.

